

Upgrading the NIST Electrostatic Force Balance

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Abstract—After the adoption of a redefined SI, electrostatic force measurements will become an ideal way to realise forces at the sub-micronewton level in a laboratory setting using an instrument such as the NIST electrostatic force balance. The balance has recently undergone a complete replacement of the control system. We describe both the new updated control system and recent improvements to analysis and data collection.

Index Terms—Electrostatic force, precision measurements, small force metrology, Redefinition of the SI.

I. INTRODUCTION

As the SI currently stands, mass and force metrology is fundamentally linked to a physical object. Small force metrology relies not only on this physical artifact, it also relies on the laborious process of subdividing to produce smaller traceable mass artifacts. With each subdivision process providing a traceable mass a factor of ten smaller, traceable mass measurements at the sub-milligram level require six or more subdivisions, each with compounding uncertainty, and the increased time and effort expended.

Small forces can also be realized directly from electromagnetic balances. Working at a force six orders of magnitude smaller than the weight of the international kilogram prototype (IPK) is no longer a direct disadvantage. This frees metrologists to concentrate on the challenges of their measurement rather than on the uncertainty in the base unit itself. An example of such an instrument is the NIST electrostatic force balance (EFB).[1]

The current SI requires a convoluted traceability path for electromagnetic balances; the measurement is first traced to electrical units then back to the IPK through measured quantities such as Planck’s constant. The proposed 2018 redefinition of the kilogram in terms of fundamental constants represents a paradigm shift of particular benefit to small force metrology. Small masses and forces can be realized with measurements directly linked to quantum standards, rather than via a long traceability path.

II. THE NIST ELECTROSTATIC FORCE BALANCE

The NIST EFB generates an electrostatic force of

$$F_z = \frac{1}{2} V^2 \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \quad (1)$$

between the plates of a concentric cylinder capacitor (See Figure 1). Where V is the potential difference across the capacitor, C is the capacitance, and z is the axial displacement of the inner electrode of the capacitor, which can be translated by a parallelogram linkage. To measure a force the balance is

Fig. 1. Schematic of the NIST electrostatic force balance.

run in two modes. In the first mode the capacitance of the main capacitor is measured as a function of position, in order to calculate $\frac{\partial C}{\partial z}$. In this mode the balance is actuated by the a potential across the auxiliary capacitor. In the second mode we measure the change in potential across the main capacitor needed to maintain a null position as a force is applied to the balance.

The balance is controlled by custom control software. This software uses a Proportional-Integral-Derivative controller (PID loop) to maintain a given position setpoint by varying the voltage across one of the capacitors (main during force measurements, auxiliary during $\frac{\partial C}{\partial z}$ determination). The old control system measured the balance position using a double-pass Michelson interferometer read with a Zygo 4104C¹ at ~ 40 kHz, and output a 16-bit ± 100 V control signal (output sample rate ~ 1.4 kHz). The 16-bit quantisation of the output voltage limited position control. The left panel of Figure 2 shows the balance control voltage while maintaining the balance null position. The force required to maintain position drifts over time (this effect is removed with linear drift correction in force measurements), the balance clearly has trouble maintaining position, at certain voltages with a spacing concurrent with the output quantisation marked with red horizontal lines.

The upgraded control system uses a custom interface to the backplane of the 4104C to increase the sample data rate to 1 MHz. The output signal is now generated from a 24-bit sigma-delta DAC updated at 1kHz. Enough position data is generated at each point to perform linear least squares fitting in real time for the derivative component of the PID loop,

¹Certain commercial equipment, instruments, or materials are identified in this paper in order to specify the experimental procedure adequately. Such identification is not intended to imply recommendation or endorsement by the National Institute of Standards and Technology, nor is it intended to imply that the materials or equipment identified are necessarily the best available for the purpose.

Fig. 2. Left: Quantisation (16-bit) of the output voltage on the old control system could result in poor position control. Red lines represent voltage discrete output levels of the DAC, black dots represent recorded voltage and position. Right: Preliminary results from the new control system with (24-bit DAC), indicate improved position control. We note, however, that the balance is running under different conditions and a fair comparison has not yet been performed.

increasing stability. The extra 6-bits on the DAC remove the quantisation issue. A rigorous comparison has not yet been performed but preliminary results (right panel of Figure 2) show improved position control.

III. CAPACITANCE GRADIENT DETERMINATION

Further improvements to the NIST EFB have been in data collection analysis for the capacitance gradient determination. During these measurements the inner electrode is translated in z by a parallelogram linkage. The linkage stops the electrode from tilting under motion and allows for direct balancing of applied and electrostatic force rather than balancing the resulting moment about a pivot. However, the linkage produces arcuate motion, and as the capacitance of a eccentric cylinders has quadratic dependence on the distance between the axes of the two cylinders, this results in a fifth order polynomial for $C(z)$.

To confirm the need to consider higher order terms and whether they can be accurately accounted for a we used an encoded translation stage to mimic the motion of a parallelogram linkage with a test capacitor. Fifth order fitting was, as expected, able to reproduce the same value for the capacitance gradient as when the electrode was linearly translated. The extra degrees of freedom in the fit result in a increased type A uncertainty.

To fit the fifth order polynomial on the NIST EFB we perform capacitance measurements at eleven discrete z positions. These results show systematic differences when processed with first, third, and fifth order fitting (Figure 3) of up to 30 ppm. For comparison the the combined standard uncertainty of the NIST EFB measurements presented in 2014 was 54 ppm.[2] We do note that the systematic effect cannot be

Fig. 3. Capacitance determinations accounting for expected fifth order polynomial terms in $C(z)$. Show systematic differences of order 30ppm compared to linear fitting, and 8ppm compared to third order fitting. These systematic differences are dependent on the precise alignment of the system and on the range over which the gradient is determined. The errorbars represent type A uncertainties ($k = 1$), as estimated from least squares fitting.

retroactively applied as its magnitude depends on the precise alignment of the balance, and many previous measurements did not determine capacitance at enough discrete z positions to be able to perform a robust fifth order fit.

IV. CONCLUSION

Preliminary work suggests that significant improvements to the control system of the NIST EFB have improved position control of the balance, allowing for more precise small force metrology on the balance. Additionally improved data collection and analysis accounts for the systematic effect of the non-linear balance motion.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We acknowledge the assistance provided by John Kramar, Prem Rachakonda, and Jon Pratt during the design of the new control system.

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